
BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

18th DEMSEE Congress

Deregulated Electricity Market Issues in South-Eastern Europe

Belgrade, Serbia

22-23 June 2026

Organized by

Mihajlo Pupin Institute

DEMSEE Congress

1. Preface

Dear participants, authors, and guests,

Welcome to the 18th DEMSEE Congress, taking place on 22–23 June 2026 in Belgrade, Serbia, at the Mihajlo Pupin Institute.

For many years, the DEMSEE Congress has served as a regional platform for the exchange of knowledge, experience, and ideas in the fields of electric power systems, electricity markets, digitalization, operation, and the development of modern energy networks.

This Book of Abstracts contains the abstracts of papers accepted for presentation at the 18th DEMSEE Congress. The contributions cover a range of current topics, including control centre operation, coordination between TSO, DSO, and RCC entities, renewable energy integration, electricity market developments, digital twins, artificial intelligence, and other advanced solutions in power systems.

We would like to thank all authors, speakers, members of the Steering Council and Scientific Committee, as well as all participants whose contributions continue to support the continuity and quality of the DEMSEE Congress.

We wish you a successful and inspiring Congress.

Igor Bundalo
Chairman of the 18th DEMSEE Congress

2. Congress Information

Congress title: 18th DEMSEE Congress

Full title: Deregulated Electricity Market Issues in South-Eastern Europe

Date: 22-23 June 2026

Venue: Mihajlo Pupin Institute, Belgrade, Serbia

Founder: Professor Thales M. Papazoglou, PhD

Chairman: Igor Bundalo

Vice-Chairman: mr Goran Jakupović

3. Steering Council

- Igor Bundalo
- mr Goran Jakupović
- mr Nikola Obradović
- Marta Gačić
- Professor Thales M. Papazoglou, PhD

4. Scientific Committee

- mr Goran Jakupović
- Professor Thales M. Papazoglou, PhD
- mr Nikola Obradović
- Igor Bundalo
- Iva Batić, PhD
- Anđela Krljaš

5. Congress Programme

Monday, 22 June 2026

09:00–10:00 Registration
10:00–10:30 Opening Ceremony
10:30–12:00 Keynote Lectures
12:00–14:00 Lunch break
14:00–17:00 Paper Presentations

Tuesday, 23 June 2026

10:00 Visit to Mihajlo Pupin Institute / Technical programme

6. Abstracts

Validation of the System Split Application through Sandbox Testing

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Serbia

Srđan SUBOTIĆ

Elektromreža Srbije JSC

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SUMMARY

This paper presents the sandbox-based testing and validation of the System Split application developed within the Horizon Europe project Reliability, Resilience and Defense Technology for the Grid (R2D2). The System Split module is designed to detect system split events and support coordinated restoration actions among Transmission System Operators (TSOs) and the Regional Coordination Centre (RCC).

The sandbox environment provides a fully isolated framework that enables safe execution, debugging, and performance testing of the application under realistic operating conditions. Within this environment, system split detection algorithms and coordination procedures can be repeatedly tested and verified without any impact on production SCADA/EMS systems.

Preliminary results confirm that the sandbox approach improves testing efficiency, enhances reliability, and provides a secure platform for continuous development and validation of real-time control center applications.

KEYWORDS

sandbox, system split, software testing, SCADA/EMS, resilience

Coordinated Security Analyses Enhancement Based on Western Balkans Power System Events

Jovana JEVREMOVIĆ, Ksenija PAPIĆ, Anđela KRLJAŠ, Tijana MILOVANOVIĆ

Security Coordination Centre SCC Ltd. Belgrade

Serbia

SUMMARY

This study analyses two significant power system incidents in the southeastern part of Europe, highlighting both operational vulnerabilities and the critical importance of regional coordination. The first, a smaller incident, took place on May 28, 2023, at the border between Montenegro and Bosnia and Herzegovina. This event revealed certain deficiencies in operational planning, protection systems, and coordination between neighbouring transmission system operators. While the disturbance did not result in any consumer disconnections or major outages, it served as an early indicator of potential risks within the interconnected regional network and emphasised the need for a thorough review of operational procedures and preventive measures.

The second incident, which occurred on June 21, 2024, had far more severe consequences. It triggered cascading outages and a voltage collapse across the transmission systems of Albania, Montenegro, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Croatia, ultimately leading to a widespread regional blackout. The event demonstrated how localized faults, if not properly managed, can escalate and propagate through interconnected networks, causing significant disruption to power supply. Importantly, the rest of the European power system was not significantly affected, highlighting the effectiveness of existing interconnections beyond the region and underscoring the resilience of the wider continental grid.

This paper presents a detailed overview of the sequence of these events and examines the technical, operational, and environmental factors that contributed to their occurrence. It analyses the recommendations proposed by the ENTSO-E expert group responsible for the post-incident investigation. These recommendations have led to the development of new operational procedures and the enhancement of existing processes, improving both reliability and efficiency. Special emphasis is placed on the improvement of regional coordination mechanisms, updated security analysis methodologies, and preventive measures aimed at minimizing the likelihood and impact of similar incidents in the future.

By integrating these improvements, transmission system operators in the region are now better equipped to respond to emergencies, mitigate cascading failures, and maintain system stability. The lessons learned from these incidents not only strengthen regional preparedness but also contribute to broader efforts to enhance the security, resilience, and sustainability of power system operations across Europe. Overall, these measures represent a significant step forward in ensuring the safe and reliable operation of interconnected power networks under increasingly complex and challenging conditions.

KEYWORDS

coordinated security analysis, regional coordination, transmission system operators (TSOs), operational planning, contingency analysis.

Application of Genetic Algorithm (GA) for Generating Unit Selection at the Perućica HPP

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Gojko BLAGOJEVIĆ

EPCG, AD Nikšić, Nikšić,

Montenegro

SUMMARY

In order to make the best possible use of the water potential and ensure the balance reserve for the needs of energy system regulation, it is necessary to optimally plan the operation of the hydroelectric power plant. The values of hydropower production are set in defined time intervals based on short-term planning obtained by optimizing the production mix from the balance responsible party, and data on water resources and availability of generators are also known. Under these conditions, optimal use of generators and the available amount of water from reservoirs should be foreseen.

In HPPs with multiple generators, the selection of generators depends on pipeline losses, mechanical losses on turbines, electrical losses on generators, etc. The goal of planning should be the optimal use of water potential and the use of generators, and the result of the optimization is flows through generators and pipelines, such that the given production of the hydroelectric power plant is ensured. This objective is described by an objective function, which is defined by a non-linear relationship of several variables, in this case the degree of utilization and the flow of each unit individually.

The obtained results for flows represent input data for further planning, mainly for planning the provision of a sufficient amount of water in the input building, for the production of the power plant, which practically means maintaining the height of the input building in the given range. The paper presents the procedure for obtaining and solving the objective function using a genetic algorithm (GA), with the simplest restrictions on the input variables. The principle of the genetic algorithm consists of evaluation, selection, crossover and mutation within a population. Through the iterative procedure of these four principles, through several generations, the solution of the objective function is obtained.

KEYWORDS

genetic algorithm, planning, generation, population, chromosome, gene, hydropower plant, generator

With the Interconnection in Operation, is there room for New Renewable Plants in Crete?

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Greece

SUMMARY

The Paper will address how the electricity supply in Crete has changed with the Interconnection and the retirement of the fossil (oil-fired) power plants that were the backbone of Crete's electricity supply. The design characteristics of the interconnection, as perceived and designed based on projected future demand, may result in significant overcapacity at present. This would be investigated. The supply of electricity in remote areas of Crete and the needs in these areas, covering different business activities (e.g., agriculture, tourism, and industry) as well as home use. The economic and social aspects affecting the choice to build/extend the grid to reach these areas versus opting for distributed generation that is heavily dependent on PV and/or Wind generation.

The Interconnection project has brought and will continue to bring significant environmental benefits and will certainly contribute to the development of Crete for years to come.

The paper will examine whether a mix of locally generated RE in Crete and electricity imported via the Interconnection could yield additional benefits compared with the island relying solely on Interconnection electricity.

KEYWORDS

interconnection, renewable energy

Joint Control of Active Power with Dual Operating Modes for the HPP Perucica

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SUMMARY

In this paper, the concept and implementation of a two-mode Joint Control of Active Power (JCAP) will be presented. The regulator is designed to enable coordinated management of active power across multiple generating units with different technical characteristics, treating the hydropower plant as a single entity. Without such a system, operators are required to manually distribute load, which results in uneven exploitation of units, increased risk of error, and limited participation in secondary and tertiary regulation.

The proposed solution introduces a dual-mode architecture that ensures both reliability and flexibility. The first mode, local power distribution, is executed directly on the PLC, where the algorithm allocates power among units according to their technical limits and current operating conditions. The second mode, planned power distribution, integrates external optimization through SPAR and the Water Management System (WMS), enabling alignment with resource management strategies and dispatcher requirements.

By combining these two modes, the JCAP provides a robust framework for stable operation, efficient resource utilization, and seamless integration into the broader power system regulation.

KEYWORDS

Joint Control of Active Power, dual-mode, hydropower plant, secondary regulation, PLC, SPAR

7. Contact Information

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8. Note

The authors are solely responsible for the content of their abstracts.